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Understanding road safety: a literature review and recommendations for City of Doncaster Council

Verity Place Graduate Management Trainee, City of Doncaster Council

Dr Ava Hodson Health Determinants Research Collaboration, University of Sheffield

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Overview

This systematic review gathers evidence around public perceptions of road safety and the impact of public health interventions, with the aim of providing recommendations for City of Doncaster Council during their development of a Road Safety Strategy.

Methods

A search of academic and grey literature between 2020 and 2025 was carried out, with search terms related to: (i) public health messages, campaigns, advertisements or education, in combination with (ii) Road safety, seatbelt use, drink or drug driving, road regulation, or road traffic collisions, and (iii) public perceptions, behaviour change and compliance or non-compliance. See Appendix 1 for the full search strategy.

The included studies were written in English and reported empirical data which explored the impact of public health interventions upon perceptions of safety, behaviour changes, and level of compliance with road safety measures. Ethical approval was not necessary because all data collected was publicly available. Qualitative content analysis was employed to extract the data into the following categories: (i) Factors influencing perceptions of road safety, (ii) Factors influencing behaviour change, (iii) Factors influencing level of compliance, and (iv) Safety outcomes (and other outcomes). This information was then divided into several themes which allowed clear discussion of the results.

Results

Sources of road safety knowledge

Sources of road safety knowledge range from formal guidance from trusted institutions, schools, and tailored training providers to informal sources including discussions with friends and family, and media broadcasts. Public knowledge of road safety measures was also attributed to the effort of the government and the provision of reliable guidance.

Knowledge and perceptions of road safety

There were some inconsistencies across knowledge of road safety and road regulations, such as correct and legal mobile phone use, and speeding laws on different road types. Perceptions of safety in the community are linked to road use and environment (i.e., road quality), where poor quality or deteriorating roads heighten perceived unsafety and concurrently encourage unsafe behaviours. With regard to positive safety behaviours, the

included evidence suggests that populations had a good knowledge of seatbelts and their proper use.

Demographic factors and individual differences influencing road safety

Demographic factors such as age and gender have a large impact road safety, perception of road safety and the impact of behaviour change interventions. Similarly, individual differences such as personality differences, pregnancy and marital status, and road user type (i.e., pedestrian, cyclist or driver) impact on the effectiveness of messaging or campaigns and overall attitudes towards road safety.

Impact and outcomes of road safety measures

Several studies investigated the impact and outcomes of specific road safety measures, including implementation of 20mph legislation and delivery of targeted interventions for young drivers. Interventions produce a range of positive outcomes including reduced speed, reduced number of cars on the road, safer driving practices and increased compliance with road safety measures (including seatbelt use).

Barriers and facilitators to behaviour change

Barriers to behaviour change include financial pressures, particularly for commercial drivers, as well as perceived discomfort of protective equipment, like helmets, which prevents their use. Lack of government promotion and negative public attitudes towards authority figures creates difficulties for preventative interventions and strategies to be successfully received by the public and implemented. On the other hand, facilitators such as targeted information campaigns, distribution of protective and supportive equipment, and video interventions were found to have a positive effect and encourage road safety behaviours.

Improving road safety

Improving road safety campaigns should mean that they are community-led, collaborative and diversified to capture a wider audience. The framing of messages is important, for example, emphasising potential losses and combining guidance with statistics can greatly influence the public. The use of schools to facilitate road safety education at a young age is very effective and should be continued and expanded where possible. Additionally, improving enforcement is critical to improving road safety and deter improper road use.

Recommendations

1. Improve knowledge, awareness and public understanding by improving education and public health messaging around road safety. Specific and targeted education can overcome some of the differences across age, gender and road user type.

2. Strengthen enforcement efforts by ensuring that deterrents are visible and known in the community. Enforcement and education should be combined, and authority figures should act as community role models.
3. Implement community-based safety measures to improve perceived road safety at a community level. This includes implementation of traffic-calming measures and creating reduced-speed zones and improving infrastructure.
4. Address financial and economic barriers to safe behaviours by providing subsidised or free protective equipment (e.g., helmets, high-visibility clothing, and other protective clothing), as well as learning around financial and personal cost of unsafe driving.

Introduction

Road safety is a critical public health concern since road traffic collisions (RTCs) account for nearly 1.2 million deaths, globally, each year (World Health Organisation [WHO], 2023). This figure demonstrates the critical need for action to improve road safety and effective strategies reduce the number of people impacted by RTCs.

Evidence suggests that road traffic casualties are ‘socially patterned’ where certain populations have greater vulnerabilities than others. For example, RTCs, and any related injuries and deaths, occur more in areas with greater socioeconomic disadvantage; more than half of all road traffic deaths are among vulnerable road users such as pedestrians and cyclists, and RTCs are the leading cause of death for children and young adults aged 5–29 years (Steinbach et al., 2011; WHO, 2023). Despite this, ensuring road safety for *all* road users is a major public health concern for national and local governments, alike.

Significant efforts have been directed toward reducing traffic-related injuries and fatalities. Methods include introducing low speed limits, enforcing use of seatbelts and implementing laws against drink-driving (Department for Transport, 2026). Road safety interventions of this kind play a vital role in influencing individual behaviours and encouraging compliance with safety regulations and thus shaping perceptions of road safety.

This review supports the development of a Road Safety Strategy for City of Doncaster Council by exploring public perceptions of road safety, as evident in the existing literature. Where apparent it explores current knowledge of safety measures, including sources of knowledge, and demographic and individual factors that impact road safety knowledge and perceptions. In addition, it presents any arising barriers and facilitators to safe practice on the road, as well as possible strategies or methods for improving road safety. By synthesising findings from UK-based and relevant international studies, the review provides a robust evidence base to inform strategic aims, targeted actions, and priority areas within the local authority’s road safety planning.

Methods

Search strategy

Two main searches were conducted as part of this review. Firstly, a search of academic literature was conducted using Ovid MEDLINE, PsycArticles and PsycINFO, and PubMed. Databases were searched from 5th November 2025 to 18th December 2025.

Search terms related to: (i) public health messages, campaigns, advertisements or education, in combination with (ii) road safety, seatbelt use, drink or drug driving, road regulation, or road traffic collisions, and (iii) public perceptions, behaviour change and compliance or non-compliance. See Appendix 1 for the full search strategy.

A second search of the grey literature was completed via Google to identify any further stand-alone guidance documents. First a Google Advanced search was conducted, in addition to individual searches on identified websites. These were webpages for: UK Government, National Highways, Think!, The Royal Society for the Prevention of Accidents, The Road Safety Foundation, and Brake.

Overall, nineteen separate grey literature searches were completed, using a variation of search terms related to perceptions of road safety and compliance with road safety measures. For all grey literature searches, the first 20 pages of results were searched. Searches were limited to studies published between 2020 and 2025 to ensure the review reflected the most up-to-date evidence.

Inclusion criteria

Articles or resources were included based on the following criteria:

1. Population: were related to drivers, pedestrians, and/or other road-users (e.g., cyclists and motorcyclists)
2. Intervention: focused on public health messaging, educational resources, interventions, advertisements or campaigns related to road safety or road safety knowledge (i.e., exploring baseline knowledge of road safety)
3. Outcomes: related to perceptions of safety, behavioural change (i.e., related to intervention or safety measure), and level of compliance with road safety measures

Only resources or articles written in English and reporting on empirical data were included (thus excluding review articles). In addition to this, studies that reported on or explored outcomes related to behaviours that are illegal or non-regulatory in the UK (for example, North American studies that explore drug-use and driving behaviours) were also excluded since they were not applicable to the UK driving context.

Data extraction and analysis

Data extraction was completed using qualitative content analysis. This method uses predetermined codes to extract data and construct meaning (Schreier, 2014). The study objectives were used to guide data extraction and was completed using the following categories: (i) Factors influencing perceptions of road safety, (ii) Factors influencing behaviour change, (iii) Factors influencing level of compliance, and (iv) Safety outcomes.

Ethical considerations

Ethical approval was not required for the literature review since all data collected was publicly available.

Results

Overall, forty-seven resources were included in the review (see Figure 1). After thematic analysis of these resources, six themes were identified from the data. These were ‘Sources of road safety knowledge’, ‘Existing knowledge and perceptions of road safety’, ‘Demographic factors and individual differences influencing road safety’, ‘Impact and outcomes of road safety measures’, ‘Barriers and facilitators to behaviour change’ and ‘Improving road safety’.

Figure 1 – Flowchart to show number of records included in review, adapted from Page et al. (2021)

Sources of road safety knowledge

Sources of road safety knowledge range from formal guidance from trusted institutions such as government bodies, schools, and tailored training providers, as well as informal sources such as discussions with friends and family, or media broadcasts (Adebiyi et al., 2025; Fylan, 2021; M. Selveindran et al., 2021; Shaker et al., 2014; Idris et al., 2013).

Findings from Adebiyi et al. (2025)'s study suggest that media broadcasts (e.g., via a dedicated 'Traffic Radio'), successfully convey the importance of seat belt use, speed limit adherence, and the avoidance of phone use while driving. However, broadcasts should be delivered in non-peak traffic times to encourage listeners to pay attention to and 'fully absorb' the information (Adebiyi et al., 2025). However, findings from Fleiter and Watson (2012)'s assessment of road fatality awareness amongst the Australian public suggests that media reports as a source of road safety information can cause confusion and, paradoxically, contribute to the public's general underestimation of road risk (Fleiter & Watson, 2012).

Fylan (2021)'s report for the Royal Society for the Prevention of Accidents (RoSPA) suggests that parents are an important source of knowledge for children about road safety and safe practices. Parents can directly educate their children by outlining safe road crossing practice and discussing the realities of road dangers. Furthermore, evidence from their school-based study in the UK, suggests that parents have the potential to also model unsafe road safety behaviours to their children like using a phone while crossing the road (Fylan, 2021).

Public knowledge of road safety measures is also attributed to the effort of the government, and their provision of "reliable information to road users" (Nzuchi et al., 2022). Other included studies also highlight the perceived importance of government influence in disseminating safety awareness and guidance; guidance around the use of protective gear, such as helmets and seatbelts, needs to be 'legislated, promoted, and enforced' (Mitra S. et al., 2023).

Knowledge and perceptions of road safety

Existing knowledge of safety measures included knowledge of speed limits, use of seatbelts and other protective measures, and driving whilst under the influence and mobile phone use. Findings indicate that there are some differences across knowledge of different road safety behaviours, as well as differences between intended and actual road safety practice.

The 2020 National Travel Attitudes Survey (NTAS), conducted by the UK Department for Transport, highlights some differences between road safety understanding and actual behaviours. For example, 93% of respondents (N = 2,647) believed they understood the

laws on mobile phone use while driving, however 25% still believed it was safe to use a phone while stationary in traffic (Department for Transport, 2020). Perceptions of ‘hands-on’ phone use whilst driving were clearer: 96% agreed it was unsafe to ‘scroll’ or use applications, and all respondents agreed it was unsafe to send text messages (Department for Transport, 2020). Public comprehension of speed-related risks was also mixed. While 82% agreed that travelling slightly over the speed limit on residential streets is unsafe, only 39% said the same for motorways (Department for Transport, 2020). On single-carriageway A-roads, 32% believed it would be unsafe to drive at the maximum 60mph limit (Department for Transport, 2020). Attitudes towards speed-enforcement also revealed a divide: although 59% agreed that speed cameras save lives, 41% felt they are mostly used to generate revenue. Respondents also indicated preferring average speed cameras over fixed installations (Department for Transport, 2020).

At a community-level, findings suggest a link between perceptions of road safety and road use and environment (i.e., road quality). Findings from the National Travel Attitudes Survey identified that individuals who perceived the deterioration of road quality (over a previous five year period) were also concerned about the number of people killed or seriously injured within walking distance of their home and support the introduction of 20mph speed limits and speed bumps to slow down traffic in the local area (Department for Transport, 2020). Concurrently, Oestreich, Torres and Ruiz-Padillo (2021) found that heightened risk perception amongst school students can be attributed to poor road conditions, which influence their road use in the community. For example, those who rely on transport to get to school perceive risk to be higher because there are more vehicles on the road and they do not have appropriate pavements and streetlights to enable them to walk (thus, diminishing their perceived safety: Oestreich et al., 2021).

Other international studies present inconsistencies in knowledge around road signs and how to interpret them, the maximum speed limits on the road, and legal alcohol driving limit (Okafor et al., 2013; Köchling et al., 2021). Delpisheh et al. (2025) suggest that key factors influencing unsafe behaviours is lack of awareness of laws, cultural attitudes, and socio-economic influences. Indeed, this review also identified several demographic and individual differences that influence the perceptions and practice of safety on the road; these are outlined below.

With regard to positive safety behaviours, the included evidence suggests that populations had a good knowledge of seatbelts and their proper use¹. In Idris et al.

¹ There are some demographic differences across actual seatbelt use, which are explained in this report.

(2013)'s study exploring seatbelt use in Nigeria, nearly all respondents knew about seatbelts and their role in preventing road traffic collisions (RTCs). The majority of participants (90% of 300 participants) knew that seatbelts are important to use and can prevent injury in the event of a collision; only small minority (7% of 300 participants) did not use a seatbelt. Similarly, the National Travel Attitudes Survey conducted by the UK Department for Transport, indicates that knowledge of seat belts is good; only 12% state that seat belts are *not* important on short journeys, and 76% stating they know how to correctly restrain a child under seven in a vehicle (Department for Transport, 2021).

Demographic factors and individual differences influencing road safety

Several demographic factors and individual differences influenced awareness of road safety measures, safe practices on the road, and compliance with safety measures. This included gender, age, road user type, and individual differences.

Gender

There were several differences across male and female participants within the included studies, for example males were more likely to engage in dangerous or reckless driving compared to females. Alonso et al. (2021) found that men were more likely to have a vehicular crash with onboard children, compared to women, as well as speed in social contexts (i.e., with friends in the car). Additionally, Varet et al. (2023) found that females value compliance with speed limits more than males, and women are more likely to support government intervention and police enforcement of road safety measures (Alonso et al., 2021). Furthermore, Ning (2024) found that women showed a more significant reduction in red-light running following the One Helmet, One Seatbelt campaign (a 2020 national campaign in China, which provided targeted road safety education for motorcyclists and cyclists), indicating that women may be more likely to change behaviours. Supporting this theory, Oestreich (2021) found that female students perceived more risks than male students. This difference in perception may explain why women are more likely to be influenced by behaviour change campaigns (Oestreich, 2021).

Age

Differences were also apparent across different age groups. For example, with increasing age, pedestrians have better road etiquette, including passing behaviours and reduced aggression to others (Zohrehvandi et al., 2023). Individuals younger than 25-years-old

were found to be the most unsafe or risky pedestrians (Liu et al., 2021). Age also increases the likelihood of compliance with road safety regulations, whereby Hagan et al. (2021) found that motorcycle riders aged between 30–39 and 40–49 years were more likely to comply with road safety regulations compared to those less than 29 years of age.

With increasing age (i.e., drivers over the age of 30), road users are also more likely to use a seatbelt (Idris et al., 2013). On the other hand, younger and teen drivers were found to engage in more dangerous driving practices, for example driving over the speed limit and using a mobile phone whilst driving and were at greatest risk of an RTC (Fanai et al., 2022; Truelove et al., 2022; Lyon et al., 2020). Lyon et al. (2020) also found that younger drivers reported engaging in behaviours related to distraction and fatigue to a much higher degree than older drivers. Evidence suggests that this may be influenced by the social desirability of reckless driving amongst peers. Accordingly, younger drivers – i.e., those aged 16–24-year-olds – were also least likely to agree with government intervention and provision of safety measures than other age groups (Department for Transport, 2020).

Type of road user

There were additional differences across road user type, for example, pedestrian, cyclist, motorcyclist and car-users. In their exploration of collision experience from motorcyclists, Shaker et al. (2014) found that 48% of motorcyclists believed car drivers to be the most likely road users to cause motorcyclists to have an accident; this was followed by large commercial vehicle drivers (i.e., lorry and truck drivers), and then motorcyclists themselves.

With regard to protective clothing (i.e., helmets), 95.8% of 238 motorcyclist participants in Hagan et al. (2021)'s study owned crash helmets, but only 51.7% wore them 'often'. This same study also found that few motorcyclists obeyed road safety regulations, and that they also consumed alcohol while riding (Hagan et al., 2021). Good compliance with road safety regulations was more common across motorcyclists who possessed a valid licence (75%) and those who owned their motorbikes (61.4%).

Finally, pedestrians and cyclists are more likely than car or van drivers to agree to government intervention and provision of safety guidance (Department for Transport, 2020). As such, for a holistic approach to building road safety, non-drivers should also be equally informed of traffic rules, be exposed to first aid knowledge and know appropriate response teams for road collisions (Fanai, 2022).

Other individual differences

Interestingly, there were additional differences in safety knowledge and practice associated with pregnancy and being an expectant parent, as well as marital status. For example, pregnancy can lead to incorrect seatbelt use, due to concerns of discomfort or myths of dangers surrounding seatbelt use while pregnant (Abdullahi et al., 2024; Koppel et al., 2025). Despite this, most participants in Koppel et al. (2025)'s study agreed that

seatbelts would reduce harm caused by a possible crash, when used. Marital status also has a significant impact upon a person's likelihood of complying with road safety measures, whereby Phelps et al. (2024) reported that married commercial motorcyclists were 2.86 times more likely to comply than those who were unmarried.

Other individual differences were identified by Vesali-Monfared et al. (2025) and include factors such as excuse-making, laziness, forgetfulness, lack of social responsibility, lack of perceived threat of RTCs, ridicule by others, and the influence of friends, neighbours and peers, which may account for variance in safe practice and road safety knowledge. In Nigeria, illiteracy, recklessness, drunkenness, and abuse of drugs are considered the main factors influencing the high rate of unsafe practices on the road (Nwagwu, 2020).

Impact and outcomes of road safety measures

Seven of the included studies provided results related to the outcomes of public health or safety interventions and are outlined here.

Three articles related to the same overarching research project, exploring the implementation of a new 20mph speed limit in Edinburgh and Belfast (Jepson et al., 2022; Milton et al., 2021; Nightingale et al., 2022). Results of this study indicate that implementing a new 20mph speed limit in Edinburgh reduced the average speed on these roads by 1.34 mph but did not reduce the number of vehicles on the road (Milton et al., 2021; Nightingale et al., 2022). The speed limit change in Edinburgh also reduced the number of collisions and casualties on the city's roads, for example, reducing fatal collisions by 23%, 33% for serious casualties and 37% of minor casualties. Additionally, support for the 20mph increased following implementation (Jepson et al., 2022). However, the study findings state that it was not possible to determine whether the speed limit change influenced people to walk or cycle more. The same scheme in Belfast found a decrease in average speed of cars by 0.91 mph (although this was not statistically significant) and a reduction in the volume of traffic within Belfast city centre as well as a reduction in collisions and casualties, although to a lesser degree than in Edinburgh (Jepson et al., 2022; Milton et al., 2021).

Four other included studies explored the impact of interventions or regulations targeted to young people, specifically. Firstly, Bonne et al. (2018) found little effect of a graduated drivers' licence (i.e., a licence that is provided to teen drivers before receipt of their 'unrestricted' licence), with no change in fatal accidents affecting teenagers after four years of implementation. However, after six years of implementation, there were decreases in total crash fatalities involving teen drivers and in the number of dead teenaged passengers in a vehicle operated by another teen. Additionally, it may be that this strategy alone is not effective in decreasing the number of teen fatalities and should be combined with other targeted public health campaigns (Bonne et al., 2018).

For other young drivers who have been identified as engaging in dangerous or reckless driving, Berlin et al. (2021)'s findings suggest that a peer-led, classroom intervention may be effective for changing distracted driving behaviours among college students. Those who attended the intervention course showed statistically significant improvement in safe practice on the road. This included refraining from talking on a mobile phone, sending text messages, using a mobile phone for activities like reading and sending emails, and more likely placed the mobile phone on silent or out of reach while driving (Berlin et al., 2021). Other targeted interventions, for example, a seatbelt awareness and learning program from the United States of America, found that teenage drivers exposed to the learning reported greater compliance with seatbelt safety measures (Phelps et al., 2024). A speeding intervention targeted at young drivers (aged 17- to 25-years-old) in Australia also found that speed awareness monitors, threat of fines, and receipt of licence points were effective, preventative countermeasures (Truelove et al., 2022).

Barriers and facilitators to behaviour change

A number of barriers and facilitators to safe practice on the road have been identified from the included studies. Barriers included limited resources (such as time, money as well as 'manpower'), inadequate law enforcement, inconsistent education and public health messaging, and poor planning for implementation of prevention strategies or road safety education. Identified facilitators include delivering safety messages via a wide range of platforms (i.e., via video, social media, and radio), as well as provision of targeted information campaigns (i.e., for motorcyclists or younger drivers). Additionally, continuous education from schools and universities, and removal financial barriers (i.e., giving free or cheaper helmets: Vesali-Monfared et al., 2025) have been found to be effective.

Barriers

Firstly, with reference to following specific safety measures, Vesali-Monfared et al. (2025) identified that helmet nonadherence (not wearing one whilst cycling or on a motorcycle) was related to unpleasant feelings (e.g., limited vision or hearing, sweating and steaming, and lack of ventilation), the (high) cost of helmets, poor helmet quality, as well as inconsistent and ineffective helmet laws.

Another identified barrier to the implementation of road safety and related laws relates to political factors. For example, public view of authority figures impacts their attitudes towards the regulations they implement – including those related to road safety. Public resistance is bolstered when these authority figures are caught breaking the rules that they set and implement (Okyere et al., 2021). Additionally, a lack of consensus on specific laws (such as seatbelt laws, as in Okyere et al. (2021)'s study) can prevent authorities from implementing the related laws effectively (Okyere et al., 2021).

Selveindran et al. (2021) also found that negative public attitudes towards RTC prevention strategies and lack of government promotion made it difficult for any preventative intervention or strategy to be successfully implemented; this indifference towards safety strategies was highest amongst younger people. Additionally, failure to enforce or promote safety laws can result in an increase in road traffic collisions as well as general non-compliance. In Vanuatu (an island in the South Pacific Ocean), this particular issue is further exacerbated by police corruption (Fanai, 2022). Furthermore, Phelps et al. (2024) suggest that low levels of compliance with road safety rules is due to no immediate consequences to non-compliance. Indeed, in the UK 2020 NTAS, 65% of respondents (N = 2,595) believed that laws on driving under the influence of drugs are not properly enforced, and 76% of people reporting that the law on mobile phone use whilst driving is not fully enforced (Department for Transport, 2021).

Facilitators

The removal of financial barriers (i.e., giving free or cheaper helmets: Vesali-Monfared et al., 2025) was found to be a large facilitator of road safety. Bishop et al. (2013) also found that once motorcycle drivers in Tanzania had been provided with free equipment, there was an increase in helmet, reflective sticker, *and* high-visibility vest usage.

Video and radio interventions have also proven to be particularly effective facilitators to behaviour change. For example, Crundall et al. (2023) reported that drivers reduced their speed and increased passing distance (i.e., the distance between the car and individual on the road whilst overtaking) around cyclists and horse riders after watching an educational video related to the topic. Similarly, radio messaging related to safe road practice had a positive influence on drivers, whereby 60% of respondents (N=500) modified their road-use behaviours (Adebisi et al., 2025).

Improving road safety

Included studies report several methods and approaches for improving road safety. These include diversifying the methods and platforms via which public health information is shared. Targeted resources should be delivered to different age groups, using road safety education in conjunction with behavioural interventions, as well as improving road infrastructure to ensure safety. For respondents in an England-based Department for Transport (2020) study, the responsibility for ensuring road safety falls to the government, who should act in local neighbourhoods to increase road safety. Interestingly, respondents believed this was also in addition to reducing traffic congestion (83%) and traffic noise (75%) and committing to improve air quality (86%).

Road safety campaigns and education are integral to improving road safety and should make use of various communication channels such as social media platforms, transport unions, religious groups, and community groups, and employ interactive methods to

foster engagement from the public (Adebiyi et al., 2025; M. Selveindran et al., 2021). Guidance could be presented in petrol stations, toll booths, roadside shops, police stations, and on road signage at junctions exits, with additional information provided via radio, television, posters and brochures, and on the internet (Shams et al., 2022). Results suggest that it is also important to consider the emotional framing of safety messages, where those framed using 'loss aversion' is effective because people attach greater weight to potential loss (Department for Transport, 2018).

Furthermore, novel safety measures, education and campaigns should be community-led and collaborative, and foster connections across traffic police, media, and religious and educational institutions; this approach should target the unique needs of vulnerable groups like pedestrians, motorcyclists, young drivers and pregnant drivers (Abdullahi et al., 2024; Adebiyi et al., 2025; Delpisheh et al., 2025; Mitra S. et al., 2023). One clear suggestion for improvement is to ensure public education programmes are taught in a range of languages to cut across cultural and religious barriers (Uzundu 2024).

Schools are also identified as having an important role in fostering road safety knowledge and safe behaviours from an early age. Firstly, classroom-based learning courses were found to be easy to implement, cost-effective and have positive impacts on road safety awareness, but learning should be continued throughout educational school years (Berlin et al., 2021; Bishop et al., 2013; Delpisheh et al., 2025; M. Selveindran et al., 2021; Uzundu 2022). Road safety education should outline to younger children how to safely cross the road via role play and demonstration, which is a method that children enjoy, and any accompanying workbooks should be picture-based and colourful (Fylan, 2021). In addition to learning, Oestrich (2021) also suggests that the school's physical environment can have an influence on perceived road safety, whereby the lack of appropriate walkways and pavements is a key determinant of safety for young people travelling to school sites (Oestreich, 2021). Additionally, the decrease of vehicle speed around schools can improve the perception of safety by students (Oestreich, 2021).

Finally, findings suggest that improvements to enforcement measures and techniques can improve overall road safety. Ning et al. (2024)'s study suggest that inclusion of enforcement measures (i.e., live-streamed enforcement) alongside educational video safety campaigns and interventions can improve compliance with safety measures and encourage safer road behaviours (Ning et al., 2024). Findings suggest that after implementing this approach, the percentage of red-light running amongst motorcyclists and cyclists was reduced (Ning, 2024). Okyere et al. (2021) similarly found that an improvement in enforcement is critical to improve road safety. The enforcement of road safety laws could be enhanced by adequately resourcing and empowering road traffic officers to perform their duties (Okyere et al., 2021). This deters people from unsafe driving behaviours and allows further intervention when people do break traffic rules to educate individuals and prevent re-offending.

Recommendations

This systematic review provides valuable insights into road safety. These can be used to create recommendations that will help shape City of Doncaster Council's Road Safety Strategy, ensuring that measures introduced can produce tangible and effective change. Based on the review findings, four recommendations have been made.

Improve knowledge, awareness and public understanding

Government-led strategies should be implemented to improve the public's understanding of a range of risks – such as speeding, alcohol limits and mobile phone rules. Approaches should be multi-modal and combine, for example, formal learning with public health campaigns in the community.

Road safety education should start in schools and continue through the community as part of long-term, collaborative learning, whilst targeting high risk areas. Education should be provided in various languages to ensure that information is accessible to all communities. To further ensure accessibility, community networks such as churches, mosques and youth centres can be used to provide education in a safe, trusted environment. Parents, caregivers and others who work with children may be a particularly useful population group to disseminate safety messages to, since they are a trusted source of information for children and young people and provide an educational foundation for safety. Additional educational interventions should be targeted at different groups to address the demographic differences across age and gender, and road user type, and behavioural and safety outcomes associated with these differences.

Importantly, it is recommended that a mix of formal and informal education channels – for example, through schools, petrol stations, via radio and television, with supporting information across the internet and social media – are used to reflect the public's diverse learning styles, levels of trust in and views of different sources, and varying access to information. Furthermore, the visibility and clarity of government guidance should be increased and promote a consistent message through local and national bodies. Messaging should be utilised to explain why resources are targeted to certain areas or populations, helping to build transparency and trust.

Strengthen enforcement efforts

Enforcement of road safety measures should be strengthened since this is key to increasing compliance with safety regulations. Findings suggest that where there are no repercussions of non-compliance, there is no deterrent.

Therefore, enforcement of regulations should be visible and consistent throughout the community. This will not only improve trust and positive attitudes towards public health messaging but improve compliance with safety messages and ensure that the public understand the consequences of non-compliance. Enforcement and education can be combined, ensuring penalties are paired with constructive behaviour-change efforts. For example, people who break the speed limit can be offered a training course to shift their attitudes and reduce reoffending. Finally, authority figures should also be encouraged to follow the regulations, to act as community role models, maintaining public trust in official guidance and the laws they promote.

Implement community-based safety measures

Infrastructural and physical road safety improvements should be made at a community-level and should involve residents and local groups wherever possible. Safe pedestrian infrastructure should be provided, especially around schools, by improving pavements, installing crossings, introducing traffic-calming measures, and creating reduced-speed zones (e.g., mandatory 20mph zones). Road infrastructure should be enhanced, particularly in high-risk areas where infrastructure concerns contribute to collisions and perceptions of unsafety in the community. Mapping exercises and further research should be done to establish where these vulnerabilities exist in Doncaster.

Address barriers to safe behaviours

Strengthened road safety education and public health messaging should be met with additional strategies to overcome the apparent barriers to the practice of safe behaviours. Strategies should address financial barriers to buying equipment, economic constraints for drivers who engage in unsafe driving, whilst also improving the quality of safety equipment.

For example, financial barriers which prevent individuals from buying safety equipment should be reduced with financial subsidisation for the purchase of helmets, high-visibility clothing, and other protective clothing. Findings suggest that this not only removes the upfront purchase cost but enables individuals to experience the benefits first-hand and can encourage future repurchase as well as positive shifts in attitudes. Additionally, the quality of safety-enhancing products can be a barrier to behaviours change. Equipment should be safe, comfortable, and accessible to improve uptake.

Similarly, economic pressures on commercial drivers create a major barrier to behaviour change. Providing alternative solutions for those facing these pressures, alongside emphasising the real financial and personal costs of road collisions, can support better understanding and encourage safer practices.

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Appendices

Appendix 1. Database search terms

[Public health AND messag(*) OR campaign(*) OR advert(*) OR education]

AND

[Road safety OR seatbelts OR Drink driving OR road regulation OR drug driving OR speeding OR collision OR road traffic collision]

AND

[Public perception(*) OR behaviour(*) change OR compliance OR non-compliance]

Appendix 2. Google Advanced and grey literature search terms

The following Google Advanced filters were applied:

- a. Language: English
- b. Year of publication: 2020-2025

Websites were searched using the following phrases, 'public perception of road safety', 'road safety compliance' and 'road safety behaviour change'.